

THE ROLE OF FAMILY, NEIGHBORHOOD, EDUCATIONAL COOPERATION IN FORMING YOUTH'S HEALTHY LIFESTYLE CULTURE.

Atakulov Mavlonbek Saitkulovich

Doctoral student of Samarkand State University
named after Sharof Rashidov.

worldstudent@mail.ru

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the educational mechanisms of the family, neighborhood, and educational institutions in the formation of a healthy lifestyle for young people have been revealed. Effectiveness of training sessions and seminars focused on personal hygiene, family spirituality and harmful diseases in educational institutions in carrying out social-political, spiritual-educational promotion of healthy lifestyle among young people has been highlighted.

Key words: society, family institution, family spirituality, moral education, healthy lifestyle, loyalty to the motherland, stability, family legislation.

At all stages of human society, the basis of society is the family and its members. All-round development of the society is determined first of all by the harmony of family and individual development. The spirituality of the family and its healthy way of life is a component of the spirituality of the people, and it is considered an important moral value and an effective means of education. That's why young people who were brought up in all households where family spirituality and healthy lifestyle were valued, stood out from others with exemplary morals.

In the East, the family has been considered a sacred place since time immemorial. If the family is healthy and strong, peace and harmony will be achieved in the society. The vital conclusions from this are not just idle talk or special emphasis, but the result of lessons learned from the pages of past history. Our president Shavkat Mirziyoev said, "The fact that many healing centers and medical madrasas have been operating in our country since ancient times, the priceless works created by our great thinkers like Abu Ali ibn Sina, and the fact that their medicine preparation and treatment methods are famous all over the world is a proof of how much our ancestors paid attention to the development of this field. gives"¹ - he says.

Since the first years of our independence, our state has been promoting the strengthening of human health, expanding the ranks of healthy people, protecting the health of mothers and children, forming a healthy lifestyle among the general public, increasing medical culture in the family, and campaigning among the general population that the health of each person is in his own hands. to do, in a word, a lot of attention is paid to the formation of a healthy society. The issue of family spirituality and healthy lifestyle has always been one of the most urgent problems in every society, moreover, this issue has risen to the level of state policy in our country. The institution of the family is one of the most important, and at the same time, responsible priorities in the policy of our independent state.

¹ Mirziyoev.Sh.M To the healthcare workers of Uzbekistan // From national recovery to national growth. T. 4. T.: "Uzbekistan", 2020, p. 381.

A lot of practical work is being done in our country to raise young people with high morale and physical strength. A healthy lifestyle in young people is a process of active work, strong physical and mental condition, the formation of a person who can overcome extremely dangerous and harmful factors and strive for maturity. In order to carry out socio-political and spiritual-educational propaganda among young people in an effective and effective manner, trainings aimed at regular implementation of medical knowledge about a healthy lifestyle, personal hygiene, family spirituality, and the negative effects of harmful diseases. It is important to inculcate the principles of a healthy lifestyle in the minds of our youth. That is why relevant topics are covered widely based on the wishes and suggestions of students, students of higher educational institutions. In the fourth direction of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021: "Educating young people who are physically healthy, mentally and spiritually developed, independent-thinking, loyal to the Motherland, with a firm outlook on life, deepening democratic reforms and increasing their social activity in the process of civil society development"² is emphasized. A healthy lifestyle is a way of life aimed at maintaining and strengthening health, organizing daily life on the basis of biological and social laws. Formation of a healthy lifestyle and implementation of its above-mentioned principles in each family is an important factor in the education of a well-rounded generation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to convey the rules of a healthy life to the young generation and explain them sufficiently.

When determining the directions of a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to determine not according to diseases, but taking into account the evolutionary progress of humanity, according to the factors that ensure the functioning of its organism and certain systems. The reason is that studying the way of development of humanity will give us practical help in rationally organizing our life today.

In addition, the stages of development of a healthy lifestyle should not be explained only by the health of body parts and longevity factors. Perhaps, in the upbringing of a person as a mature person, it is important to form a healthy spiritual life and analyze the factors of its development. Today, in our society, important attention is paid to educating a healthy generation, forming the spirituality of a free citizen, raising the moral and educational work to a high level, and raising mature people. "Educating a healthy generation," writes M. Kholmatova, "means building the foundation of a great state, the foundation of a prosperous life." "Education of a healthy generation includes two aspects: raising the young generation to be physically healthy and bringing them to adulthood by making them spiritually mature."³

The large-scale reforms being implemented in our country depend first of all on educating young people to be mature in all aspects. The fact that new methods and programs are being implemented in the educational system serves as a guarantee of developments in this field. In particular, the implementation of the "concept of family-neighborhood-school cooperation" in our country serves as a model based on new approaches. The importance and relevance of the issue today is that the socio-political activity of young people, especially students, the development of a well-rounded generation, the development of mature personnel in all

² A scientific-methodical treatise on the study of the state program on the implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the "Year of communication with the people and human interests" in 2017-2021. Tashkent Spirituality 2017 p. 203.

³ Kholmatova M. Culture of family relations and education of a healthy generation. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2000.- B. 20.

respects, and the development of new opportunities for the cooperation of family and community institutions in educating them to follow a healthy lifestyle are of urgent importance.

Fundamental reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan aim to protect the interests of the society and the state, educate a morally sound generation who will selflessly work for the development of the country and the well-being of the people. Strengthening the cooperation of the "family-neighborhood-education" institution in raising a healthy generation in our country is the guarantee of the best results and results. The directions implemented by our government in this regard are as follows:

Improving the legal framework for ensuring cooperation between family, neighborhood, educational institutions, strengthening methodological support aimed at strengthening cooperation;

Increasing the social activity of young people and parents in the family;

Material and moral support for families in need of social protection;

Improving the content of spiritual and educational activities aimed at raising a mature generation, creating a mechanism for increasing its effectiveness;

Effective use of mass media and modern information technologies in raising a healthy generation.

Today in our country special attention is being paid to the role of family and neighborhood institutions in the life of society and their social tasks. Strengthening the family-neighborhood-educational institution cooperation in raising a healthy generation in our country serves as a guarantee of results. A person should fulfill social duties, make his children healthy, have a healthy lifestyle, and create conditions for the material and spiritual development of his children. This cannot be achieved without improving the culture of family relations. The family is an important social institution that brings up a healthy generation. Therefore, a healthy family environment is important, along with other factors, for a person to live in good health.

Young people who have a healthy education in a healthy social and spiritual environment will become real people who can contribute to the development of the country and carry out the interests of the society in proportion to their own interests. For this, it is necessary to create a mature, healthy and strong family that will raise that healthy generation. Our first president, Islam Karimov, said that "it is natural that the foundation of sacred concepts such as goodness and goodness, nobility and kindness, honor and kindness, which determine the character, nature and outlook of a child, should be settled in the family environment."⁴

If the family is healthy - the society is strong, if the society is strong - the country is stable. Neighborhood is a bridge connecting a person with society, and it is the largest generous corner and incomparable Motherland that educates in this spirit. Stability and peace reign in the state only when the neighborhood and the country are strong. One of the urgent tasks of today is to increase the knowledge of young people who are starting a family about the basics of family law, a healthy lifestyle, and raising children. The reason for this is that nowadays young people get married without having the concepts of family law, duties of husband and wife, responsible family literacy, and medical culture.

⁴ Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an inexhaustible power. - T.: "Spirituality", 2008.

Everyone wants their family to be happy, prosperous and strong. But we all know very well that it is very difficult to build a family, raise patriotic, intelligent, righteous children and bring them to maturity. It can be said without a doubt that the family is the backbone of civil society. Because not only a person is born in this holy place, but he is educated mentally and spiritually. "The stronger the family, the more stable the society and the faster it develops. A person gets his knowledge about the world around him, his first concepts of spirituality and morality, his initial ideas about good and bad from his family. ⁵ Today, special attention is paid to preventive examination, detection and treatment of long-term diseases, implementation of a healthy lifestyle, as well as prevention of smoking, drinking and drug addiction, early and marriage between relatives, prevention of AIDS. It is known that the purpose of starting a family is not only for two young people to live happily and together, but also to give birth to healthy children and build a strong family. However, there are many components and compounds in the formation of a mature environment, and at the same time, the health of the two young people is of great importance. Thanks to the independence, the traditions of neighborhood and neighborhood are formed in a new spirit, and they play an important role in strengthening family relationships and in all weddings, celebrations, sympathizing and supporting each other. Neighborhood is in the leading position in controlling such qualities as respect for elders and elders, maintaining harmony in family relations. After all, every Uzbek child receives his initial education from his family and neighborhood.

When a person abandons his health and destiny to the cruel vortex of life's flow, sacrifices his health to his harmful habits, it is the disintegration of a person as a person and his face to the bottom. When a person abandons his health and destiny to the cruel vortex of life's flow, sacrifices his health to his harmful habits, it is the disintegration of a person as a person and his face to the bottom.

In conclusion, we emphasize that strengthening the cooperation of "family-neighborhood-educational" institutions is one of the most effective ways to create a culture of healthy lifestyle among young people. This trio is the cradle that can raise the morale of the society, especially the youth, by creating a healthy environment. It will be possible to educate young people with high spirituality only if we effectively use all available opportunities and tools to conduct education in our country at the level of modern requirements.

⁵ Musurmonova O. Priorities of family-neighborhood-educational institution cooperation in raising a healthy generation in the family // Materials of the republic-wide scientific-practical conference on the topic "The role of the family in preparing young people for family and parenthood". - T., 2013. - B.217.

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